

EARTH OBSERVATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TRANSFORMATION OF THE EXTRACTIVE INDUSTRY AND CHALLENGES

by

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Society and new European Union (EU) regulations demand a transition of the extractive sector, whereas at the same time resources are urgently needed. Due to the technological advances both in sensors and in image processing and analysis tools, Earth Observation (EO) data has a rapidly increasing potential in various fields, and the extractive sector is one of them. Lower ore grades, environmental restrictions, health and safety obligations, technological efficiency and social acceptance are some factors that will eventually impose the adoption of innovations in mining during the whole supply chain and mine life cycle (Steen et al., 2019). Nowadays, EO data and remote sensing techniques provide the capability to effectively monitor mining activities and their compliance with respective guidelines during their life cycle while being non-invasive and cost-effective, throughout all mine phases. Yet there isn't any integrative approach where the scientific knowledge of EO methods and applications systematically serves as tools for transforming the extractive industry. Therefore, besides the technical developments and implementation of innovative methods for analysing EO data, research in the 'Secure and Sustainable Supply of Raw Materials for EU Industry' (S34I - <https://s34i.eu/>) project aims to unlock the potential of EO data to support the sustainability transition of the extractive industry. An expected outcome also lies in decreasing supply chain risks and increasing transparency for stakeholders, thereby contributing to the achievement of the social license to operate (SLO). To do that, social survey methods like interviews and questionnaires are implemented to capture the viewpoint of multidisciplinary stakeholders, highlighting the most crucial concerns and identifying potential opportunities to address them through EO. Moreover, collecting the existing datasets and the technical requirements corresponding to each use case defines the specifics of implementing EO data at each site and supports the technical part of the project with the relevant information to meet their objectives. The considering workflow is divided into four tasks.

The first task aims to identify a framework for the current and potential use of EO data in the extractive sector, operating both as a technological tool and sustainability reinforcer. Sustainable development, circular economy principles related to waste and materials, and social engagement actions concern not only the mining industry but also the public and the authorities. Joint legislation and company strategies are working towards the transformation of the sector.

The analysis of the mining value chain involved a multi-level approach to EO data use and its advantages. Initially, sustainability and circularity topics were listed, followed by key points for gaining social acceptance in the extractive industry. Indicators were filtered from official reporting systems and relevant literature, focusing on EO data applications in mining. Each indicator and subcategory were explored using literature sources, along with a description of the methods employed. The technical characteristics and outcomes of each case study are mentioned in the corresponding indicator. For instance, following the sustainability categorization, under the Social scope, classes like H&S (Health & Safety), Transparency/communication and community positive impact are mentioned, getting more detailed subsequently. Additional information, like online news and company reports was used to map the current industrial perception of EO data and remote sensing techniques. In the spotted topics, EO data directly contributes to the extractive industry by being a cost and time-effective tool that provides accurate results for monitoring the operation, resulting in the industry's transition.

The second task under the project aims to identify how EO-based methods can promote transparency in communication and social responsibility. In addition, the project will determine how the EO method can provide effective monitoring and independent assessment of mining activities to ensure responsible mining. A bibliographic review evaluated how EO methods have been used by mining companies, authorities, and Non-governmental organisations (NGOs) to monitor mining activity, their reliability and problematics, and their relevance to support SLO at different stages of mining operations.

The research shows that companies use EO methods mainly when operating in sensitive environments or for monitoring environmental impacts, but also for monitoring low-accessible areas and dams. Authorities and NGO's use EO data to monitor industrial activity, especially to point out transcending activities and environmental impacts. Some limitations and uncertainties in EO data use and data interpretation emerged from the study. To gain a deeper understanding, a diverse group of stakeholders is directly engaged. Interviews, focus group discussions and questionnaires run in the local language at some of the project sites. Data collection is accomplished via direct contact with their representatives through customised invitations, highlighting the relevance of their organisation's input. In Finland, for a wider audience, a link to a questionnaire is published in the local newspaper and an informal colloquial approach also being tested (Fig. 1). Expected outcomes are raising awareness of the EO-based methods amongst companies and authorities, so they use them when applicable. There has been reluctance to participate in the survey or in engaging in the discussion from all stakeholders. From the first results, it seems that the community is aware of UAVs and satellites to some

GTK

Kaivosympäristöjen tarkkailu ilmasta käsin - kerro mielipiteesi tutkimushankkeelleme

Kehitämme uusia menetelmiä, joiden avulla parannetaan kauko-kartoitusaineistojen hyödynnettävyyttä malmitutkimuksessa, sekä toimivien, suljettavien ja suljettujen kaivosalueiden ympäristövaikutusten tarkkailussa.

EU-tasoisella kyselyllä tutkitaan ihmisten tietämystä ja näkemystä kaukokartoituksen käytöstä kaivosympäristöjen tutkimuksessa.

Sinun mielipiteesi on tärkeä! Vastaa kyselyyn linkin kautta tai skanna QR-koodi.

<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/S34iAijela>

S34i

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Figure 1: Survey in Finland

extent, but it is a difficult matter in which some do not feel having enough expertise and ability to provide their own views of the matter. As the project addresses both land exploration and shallow waters systematic mineral exploration, this raises the need to consider an integrative methodology of shallow waters and land-use planning for economic usage of these areas, such as fishing and tourism, and other use needs to ensure responsible mining. It will consider local perception, land-sea connectivity, as well as environmental challenges related to the exploration campaign of respective CRMs. Thus, Task 3 focuses on the shallow waters site. Rias Baixas (Spain) has suitable geological conditions (Fig. 2) onshore or offshore for significant CRM mineralisation (EC, 2020). Conventional methods of marine minerals exploration are costly and time-consuming and can have environmental impacts on ecosystems, hefty vehicles circulating on the seafloor (Miller et al., 2018). Sea mining development and its technological solutions are being discussed lately, despite the concern about the impacts on the ecosystem on the seabed (Kleiv and Thornhill, 2022). Underwater hyperspectral imaging (UHI) is a promising and non-invasive tool for the automated identification of diverse features in the seafloor in scales varying from millimetres to hundreds of kilometres, providing close-range observations (Montes-Herrera et al., 2021).

Figure 2: Rias Baixas geological map

The research methodology adopted is a combined method developed in two phases. The first consists of a survey applied to the stakeholders of the Ria de Vigo area, whereas the second phase will be a follow-up interview study. Answers will be analysed statistically to gather opinions, concerns, and suggestions that can provide guidelines for better communication between the stakeholders and exploration companies or researchers. The questionnaire was elaborated and validated, and inter-observer reliability was defined and is now being applied to stakeholders of the area. A follow-up study involving in-person interviews is planned to take place later. The content analysis will be conducted with inter-observer reliability. The results of the survey will provide insights into the knowledge and perception of the local community about the needs and use of mining and remote sensing methods applied to mining, as well as the doubts and concerns of the stakeholders. The results will demonstrate the potential of EO data, best practices and requirements.

The importance of the last task lies in the application's impact of EO technologies in mining, with several benefits, such as reduced operation risks and the impact on the environment, increased digitalization and process efficiency of mining operations. The challenges that need to be faced are a lack of clear value propositions, a lack of understanding of the limitations of EO, and insufficient user maturity and accuracy of EO data. Forms developed for each pilot site will try to gather relevant information from the sites to best adapt the EO technologies to the technical requirements and key objectives that the sites want to achieve, and all the information collected will be used in the rest of the project tasks to better understand the requirements and needs of each site. The methods are based on:

- Sites identification: different sites have been identified and the corresponding owner;
- Characteristics of each site: general information was collected on each site to define the exact location and geological and mining characteristics;

- Forms elaboration according to the mining phases: for each mining phase, a form has been elaborated according to the stage of the mining phase, and different questions regarding the technical requirement have been formulated;
- End-users' identification: end-users from each site have been located and identified;
- Deliver the forms to the end-users: once the forms have been completed, one form per site has been sent to the end-users identified;
- Collect and analyse the information obtained from the end-users: the final step is to analyse the information received from the sites. All the information and data received is compiled into a form that describes the main requirements expected of each site.

The outcomes expected to be obtained in this task will be the definition of the requirements from each site for building trustable EO-derived information to support the mining permitting processes. The information will be used to develop a more specific EO data analysis workflow for each site and its needs according to the mining phase. Gathered data will serve other parts of the S34I project to elaborate a more accurate system with all needs covered.

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